

1 **Utilisation of citrus compost-based growing media amended with *Trichoderma harzianum* T-**
2 **78 in *Cucumis melo* L. seedling production**

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12

13 **Abstract**

14 Two citrus composts (C1: composed of 40% citrus wastes, 20% sludge obtained from a citrus
15 industry waste-water treatment facility and 40% green residues; C2: composed of 60% citrus
16 wastes and 40% green residues, and no sludge) and their water extracts amended with
17 *Trichoderma harzianum* T-78 (*T. harzianum* T-78) were assayed in order to verify if these
18 composts could act as a partial substitute for peat-based growing media as well as enhance
19 suppressiveness against *Fusarium wilt* in the production of melon (*Cucumis melo* L.) seedlings
20 at greenhouse nurseries. Over a 43-day growth cycle of melon seedlings, measurements were
21 taken of the nutriactive effect (the capability of a substrate to express additional and/or
22 synergistic nutritional and biostimulating effects), the pathogen incidence (percentage of fresh
23 weight loss of melon plants grown on treatments infected with *Fusarium oxysporum* with
24 respect to the same treatment without inoculation of the phytopathogen) and the trend of the
25 *T. harzianum* T-78 population. A nutriactive effect was observed in the tested citrus compost-
26 based growing media (96% and 112% plant weight increase with respect to peat for C1Th and
27 C2Th, respectively). Pathogen incidence was significantly lower in C2Th than peat (12%
28 compared to 33%), while no difference was observed in C1Th. The *T. harzianum* T-78 population
29 showed a significant decrease at the first sampling time compared to the initial quantity (from
30 106 to 105 CFU g⁻¹), but later recovered over time. These results demonstrate that the
31 combination of citrus compost and *T. harzianum* T-78 can be a viable alternative to peat and can

32 minimise the application of chemicals necessary to control *Fusarium* wilt in greenhouse
33 nurseries for melon seedling production.

34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 *Fusarium* wilt of melon is a highly destructive disease and causes great economic loss for
37 farmers. Except for soil fumigation, there are no chemical treatments to control the disease.
38 Management strategies are focused on prevention through the use of resistant rootstocks or
39 biological practices such as composted soil amendments (Pascual et al., 2000; Tjamos et al.,
40 2004; Ros et al., 2005; Suarez-Estrella et al., 2007). Due to the nutrient content and biopesticide
41 effect of compost (Hoitink and Fahy, 1986; Termorshuizen et al., 2006), its use as a growing
42 media could decrease the incidence of *Fusarium* wilt of melon seedlings under nursery
43 conditions and could potentially replace (at least partially) non-renewable peat media (Garcia-
44 Gomez et al., 2002; Tittarelli et al., 2003). This would decrease costs and the dependence on
45 chemical inputs. Composting of organic residues from the citrus-processing industry has been
46 investigated in recent years due to the environmental issues associated with the increased
47 yearly production of citrus fruits (Calabretta et al., 2004; Tittarelli et al., 2002). Composts derived
48 from agricultural and agroindustrial wastes are generally free of xenobiotics and excessive heavy
49 metal concentrations (Ntougias et al., 2008). Bernal-Vicente et al. (2008) reported that potting
50 media composed of citrus compost partially reduced the level of disease by *Fusarium oxysporum*
51 f. sp. *melonis* and provided a biostimulant effect on melon seedlings.

52 To enhance the suppressive potential of composts, and thus improve the efficacy of disease
53 control, it has been proposed to enrich these composts with specific strains of biological control
54 agents (BCAs) (Khan et al., 2004). *Trichoderma* spp. are among the most studied fungal BCAs
55 and are commercialised and labelled as biopesticides, biofertilizers and/or soil amendments
56 (Harman et al., 2004; Lorito et al., 2004). These fungi are opportunistic, avirulent plant
57 symbionts. They function as parasites and are antagonists of many phytopathogenic fungi, thus
58 protecting plants from disease. They can adapt to recalcitrant organic matter due to their high
59 efficiency in nutrient utilisation and capacity to modify growing media characteristics (Benítez
60 et al., 2004). Certain *Trichoderma* spp. can provide advantages such as rapid colonization of the
61 rhizosphere by the BCA within the stable, pre-existing microbial communities, control of
62 pathogenic and competitive microflora, and improvement of plant health and root growth
63 (Harman et al., 2004).

64 The main aim of this paper was to demonstrate the potential use of two citrus composts
65 amended with the BCA microorganism *Trichoderma harzianum* T-78 (*T. harzianum* T-78) as a
66 growing media for melon seedlings (*Cucumis melo* L.) and suppressive substrate against
67 fusarium wilt under greenhouse conditions. In addition, water extracts obtained from both
68 citrus composts and applied by fertigation to peat growing media inoculated with *T. harzianum*
69 T-78 were also investigated in order to evaluate their effects on melon plant growth, with and
70 without *F. oxysporum* inoculation, under greenhouse nursery conditions.

71

72 **2. Methods**

73 *2.1. Fungal strains*

74 The biological control agent (BCA) *T. harzianum* T-78 was isolated from agricultural soil and
75 deposited in the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT 20714). It was immobilized in bentonite
76 following the protocol for its addition to compost and peat described by Bernal-Vicente et al.
77 (2009). The organic materials were inoculated with the immobilized *T. harzianum* T-78 to
78 achieve a final concentration of 10⁶ CFU g⁻¹. The phytopathogen *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *melonis* (*F.*
79 *oxysporum*) was isolated from melon plants expressing disease symptoms (Nash and Snyder,
80 1962). One disc (5 mm) of 7-day old mycelia grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA) (PDA Scharlau
81 (Spain) 40 g L⁻¹, autoclaved at 121 C for 20 min, and amended with 100 mg L⁻¹ sterilized
82 streptomycin) was suspended in 100 mL of potato dextrose broth (PDB) (PDB, Scharlau (Spain)
83 24 g L⁻¹, autoclaved at 121 C for 20 min, and amended with 100 mg L⁻¹ sterilized streptomycin)
84 in a flask and incubated at 25 C on a rotary shaker for 5 days until the liquid medium was brown–
85 pink in colour. Conidia were recovered by centrifugation (6000g, 20 min), rinsed twice with
86 sterile distilled water and filtered through 101 quartz wool. The final inoculated concentration
87 was 2.9 x 10⁴ CFU g⁻¹ of organic material.

88 *2.2. Composts*

89 Two citrus composts were used for potting media as a partial substitute for peat. C1 compost
90 contained 40% citrus wastes (a mixture of citrus pulp and skins from the citrus industry), 20%
91 sludge obtained from a citrus industry waste-water treatment facility and 40% green residues
92 (pruning from citrus trees and ornamental shrubs); C2 compost contained 60% citrus wastes and
93 40% green residues, and no sludge. The main physiochemical and chemical characteristics of the
94 composts are shown in Table 1.

95 The specific composting process was described by Tittarelli et al. (2003). Compost water extracts
96 were obtained by placing compost in distilled water (1:1 v:v) for 12 h at room temperature and
97 filtering through a mesh.

98 *2.3. Experimental design*

99 The experiment was carried out in a growth chamber at 25 C with a 16 h photoperiod. Six
100 polystyrene containers (10 wells per container) were used for each treatment, considering each
101 container as one unit. One melon seed was sown in each well of the polystyrene containers.
102 Treatments were: (peatTh, control treatment) peat inoculated with *T. harzianum* T-78 (106 CFU
103 g⁻¹); (C1Th) mixture of peat and compost C1 (4:1 w:w) inoculated with *T. harzianum* T-78 (106
104 CFU g⁻¹); (C2Th) mixture of peat and compost C2 (4:1 w:w) inoculated with *T. harzianum* T-78
105 (106 CFU g⁻¹); (C1ThWE and C2ThWE) peat inoculated with *T. harzianum* T-78 (106 CFU g⁻¹) and
106 treated with C1 and C2 compost water extract, respectively.

107 All the treatments were irrigated three times a week. For each irrigation period, 200 mL of water
108 containing compost extracts were used in treatments C1ThWE and C2ThWE, 200 mL of distilled
109 water in C1Th and C2Th, and 200 mL of nutrient solution in the PeatTh treatment. The nutrient
110 solution was prepared in accordance with a specific fertilization protocol for commercial melon
111 seedling production and was applied to overcome the nutritional gap between peat and the
112 compost/peat growing media.

113 Three of the six polystyrene containers for each treatment were infected by *F. oxysporum* (2.9
114 x 10⁴ CFU g⁻¹) 15 days after sowing (DAS), when the second leaf of the plant appeared. At 30,
115 37 and 43 DAS, 20 melon plants were weighed and potting media was collected and stored at 4
116 C until microbiological analysis.

117 The nutriactive effect, defined as the capability of a substrate to express additional and/or
118 synergistic nutritional and biostimulating effects (Bernal-Vicente et al., 2008), was estimated as
119 the increased percentage of weight in melon plants grown with the different treatments with
120 respect to the control peat inoculated with *T. harzianum* T-78. The *F. oxysporum* incidence was
121 estimated as the percentage of fresh weight loss of melon plants grown on treatments infected
122 with *F. oxysporum* with respect to the same treatment without inoculation of the
123 phytopathogen. Biocontrol effect was determined by subtracting the pathogen incidence from
124 100. The population (colony forming units, CFUs) of *T. harzianum* T-78 was measured in order
125 to evaluate and relate it to plant growth, nutriactive effect and *F. oxysporum* incidence. *T.*
126 *harzianum* T-78 quantification was estimated by serial dilutions of growing media in sterile
127 quarter-strength Ringer solution followed by a plate count technique using PDA (39 g L⁻¹, Rose

128 Bengal 50 mg L⁻¹; autoclaved at 120 C for 20 min and amended with 100 mg L⁻¹ sterilized
129 streptomycin).

130 2.4. Statistical analysis

131 ANOVA and Tukey post hoc tests ($P < 0.05$) were used for comparisons between all treatments
132 at each sampling time (SPSS 15.0, SPSS Inc.).

133 3. Results

134 3.1. Plant growth and nutriactive effect

135 Treatments C1Th and C2Th not infected with *F. oxysporum* showed higher growth values with
136 respect to the PeatTh treatment throughout the whole cultivation cycle of the melon seedlings.
137 The C2Th treatment had significantly higher weight than C1Th (average of 30.6% for
138 measurements at 30, 37 and 43 DAS, Table 2).

139 For the compost water extract treatments, C2ThWE showed plant growth values substantially
140 higher than PeatTh (control treatment) throughout the experiment, while the plant growth of
141 C1ThWE was comparable to the control treatment. Compost water extracts were characterised
142 by significantly lower plant weight compared to their respective treatments (C1Th and C2Th).
143 For the nutriactive effect (Table 3), the C2Th treatment showed higher values than the C1Th
144 treatment at the first sampling time (30 DAS).

145 However, the difference between the two treatments was reduced as time elapsed (Table 3).
146 C2ThWE was comparable to C1Th at the first sampling (30 DAS), while C1ThWE more closely
147 resembled to the control treatment (PeatTh).

148 3.2. Disease suppression

149 In the presence of *F. oxysporum*, the assayed treatments showed significantly higher plant
150 weight compared to the PeatTh treatment, with the exception of treatment C1ThWE at 37 and
151 43 DAS (Table 4). Plant weight of the C2Th treatment was significantly higher than C1Th, and
152 both the compost treatments showed significantly higher plant weight than their respective
153 compost water extract treatments (Table 4). The fresh plant weight values of C2ThWE were
154 comparable to those of C1Th.

155 In general, the pathogen incidence (the percentage of plant weight loss in infected plants with
156 respect to the non-infected ones) increased over time (Table 5). As far as the differences among
157 treatments are concerned, at 30 DAS, the two C1 compost-based growing media treatments
158 (C1Th and C1ThWE) showed significantly lower values than the control and the two C2

159 compostbased growing media treatments. This demonstrates that compost C1 was able to
160 reduce the pathogen incidence at an early growing stage, but was not able to keep this property
161 over time. Conversely, at 37 and 43 DAS, the two C2 compost-based growing media treatments
162 showed lower pathogen incidence than the control treatment (PeatTh) and the two C1 compost-
163 based growing media treatments. Pathogen incidence values were 8.2% and 0.4% (37 DAS) and
164 12.0% and 0.3% (47 DAS) for C2Th and C2ThWE, respectively (Table 5). These results indicated
165 that C2 compost was able to express its pathogen control potential in the last phase of the melon
166 seedlings growing cycle, which is commercially more important.

167 Comparing the solid organic matrix to their water extracts in both composts, the pathogen
168 incidence behaviour showed a different trend. The C2ThWE treatment showed lower *F.*
169 *oxysporum* incidence than its respective solid organic matrix (Table 5), while C1ThWE showed
170 the higher pathogen incidence (not significantly different than PeatTh), than its solid matrix
171 (except at 37 DAS).

172 3.3. Quantification of *T. harzianum* T-78

173 At 30 DAS the size of the *T. harzianum* T-78 population in all treatments not inoculated with *F.*
174 *oxysporum* (Table 6) decreased by one order of magnitude in comparison to the initial starting
175 quantity (average inoculation size at 0 DAS: 6 log₁₀ CFU g⁻¹ as reported in the materials and
176 methods section). After the first time point, the size of the *T. harzianum* T-78 population
177 increased throughout the rest of the experiment in all treatments. At the end of the experiment
178 (43 DAS), both the compost-based growing media treatments (C1Th and C2Th) showed
179 significantly lower values (one order of magnitude) than their respective compost water extract
180 (C1ThWE and C2ThWE) and the control (PeatTh) treatments (Table 6). When inoculated with *F.*
181 *oxysporum*, the compost-based growing media treatments (C1Th and C2Th) and compost water
182 extract (C1ThWE and C2ThWE) treatments showed a significant increase in the *T. harzianum*
183 population with respect to the control (PeatTh) at 30 DAS. Similarly to the non-inoculated
184 treatments, at 37 and 43 DAS, both the compost-based growing media treatments (C1Th and
185 C2Th) showed significantly lower values (of one order of magnitude) than their respective
186 compost water extract (C1ThWE and C2ThWE) and the control (PeatTh) treatments (Table 6).

187 4. Discussion

188 4.1. Plant growth and nutriactive effect

189 The weight of melon seedlings, grown in compost-based growing media were higher than
190 seedlings grown in peat-based growing media. This is probably attributed to a combined or
191 synergistic effect of the composts and *T. harzianum* T-78 (Tables 2 and 3).

192 The nutriactive effect shown by the citrus composts has been attributed to the increased
193 nutrient content of the compost compared to peat and the presence of hormone-like
194 compounds which were reported as an increase in melon plant weight by 78% when compared
195 to peat (Bernal-Vicente et al., 2008). In the same manner, the increase in the nutriactive effect
196 shown with the inoculation of *T. harzianum* T-78 is reported to be due to the capacity of some
197 isolates of genus *Trichoderma* to produce organic compounds which possess biostimulant
198 properties and hormone-like characteristics (Harman, 2000; Resende et al., 2004). Another
199 hypothesized mechanism of the nutriactive effect is that *T. harzianum* T-78 improves the
200 mineralization pattern of organic matter in compost, resulting in an increased release of
201 nutrients for utilisation by plants (Kleifeld and Chet, 1992). Bernal-Vicente et al. (2009)
202 demonstrated that the same *T. harzianum* strain used in this experiment increased melon plant
203 weight by 27% in comparison to peat.

204 Results reported in this paper demonstrate that the combination of the same citrus compost
205 types used by Bernal-Vicente et al. (2008) and the same *T. harzianum* strain used by Bernal-
206 Vicente et al. (2009) promoted the growth of melon seedlings.

207 Moreover, the nutriactive effect showed at the end of the experiment (43 DAS) by C1Th and
208 C2Th treatments (96.4% and 111.9%, respectively (Table 3)) was similar to the sum of the effects
209 determined by the composts and the *T. harzianum* strain when they were applied independently
210 of the other (Bernal-Vicente et al., 2008; 2009).

211 The treatment C2Th showed higher melon plant weight (Table 2) and nutriactive effect (Table
212 3) than that of C1Th treatment. These results were unexpected because the presence of sewage
213 sludge in compost C1 should have provided a higher amount of available nutrients for the plant
214 growth in the C1Th treatment. According to Bernal-Vicente et al. (2008) these composts (C1 and
215 C2) as base components of growing media did not show significant differences in the growth of
216 melon seedlings. This behaviour is probably due to the presence of sewage sludge in the C1
217 compost, that could have originated changes in the compost itself and in the derived growing
218 media (C1Th) characteristics (Gallardo-Lara and Nogales, 1987) and then reduced the *T.*
219 *harzianum* effect on plant yield. Additionally, the presence of sewage sludge might have
220 determined a more rapid decomposition of biostimulant compounds, thus reducing the
221 nutriactive effect (Pascual et al., 2000; Ros et al., 2005; Bernal-Vicente et al., 2009).

222 According to Bernal-Vicente et al. (2008) the melon plants weight and nutriactive effect were
223 higher in the C1Th and C2Th treatments compared to the respective water extract treatments
224 (C1ThWE and C2ThWE; Table 2 and 3). This could be due to a possible salt accumulation and the
225 fact that the hormone-like compounds of the C1 and C2 composts would not be totally water
226 extractable, due to their high molecular weight and their capability to form stable complexes
227 with humic substances (Atiyeh et al., 2002). Furthermore, since only low amounts of
228 lignocellulosic compounds are water extractable (Hendriks and Zeeman, 2009), *T. harzianum*
229 could have had a limited quantity of substrate available to meet its energy and nutrients needs
230 in the C1ThWE and C2ThWE treatments (Harman et al., 2004). Therefore, the potential activity
231 of the inoculated strain would have been reduced, producing fewer amounts of nutriactive
232 compounds to induce melon plant growth.

233 *4.2. Disease suppression*

234 Biological control involves the use of beneficial organisms, their genes, and/or products such as
235 metabolites that reduce the negative effects of plant pathogens and promote positive responses
236 by the plant (Alabouvette et al., 2006). These beneficial microorganisms can be naturally present
237 in the growing media, as demonstrated in the two citrus compost-based growing media (Bernal-
238 Vicente et al., 2008), or artificially incorporated into the growing media (Alabouvette et al.,
239 2006). *Trichoderma* are among the most commonly used antagonist fungi, due to their ability to
240 protect plants and contain pathogen population under a wide-range of conditions. They produce
241 a number of biologically active compounds, including cell wall degrading enzymes and secondary
242 metabolites (Vinale et al., 2008). Compost extracts can also contain biocontrol agents as well as
243 unidentified chemical factors, which appear to play a role in fungal suppression (Shen, 2000).
244 Although the mechanisms by which these extracts provide control remain unknown (Boulter et
245 al., 2000), they could potentially be attributed to a combination of competition for nutrients,
246 antibiosis, and extracellular lytic enzyme production (Cronin et al., 1996) or to low molecular
247 weight compounds that lyse fungal structures (Baziramakenga and Simard, 1998).

248 Suppression of diseases caused by *F. oxysporum*, has been reported for a wide-range of
249 composts (Noble and Coventry, 2005; Yogev et al., 2006; Termorshuizen et al., 2006). Bernal-
250 Vicente et al. (2008) showed that melon seedlings grown in composts C1 and C2-based growing
251 media and their water extracts diminished *F. oxysporum* incidence due to their biotic (antibiosis
252 and mycoparasitism) and abiotic components. Compost effects against plant pathogens are also
253 attributed to niche competition or plant acquired and/or induced resistance (Alabouvette et al.,
254 2006).

255 Fusarium incidence was significantly lower in the C2 compost based treatments (C2Th and
256 C2ThWE) than in the C1 compost based treatments (C1Th and C1ThWE), although C1ThWE
257 showed a similar Fusarium incidence than PeatTh. This evidence can be attributed to the
258 different composition of the two composts. In fact, in the C1 compost based treatments, the use
259 of sewage sludge might have determined a higher microbial activity (Pascual et al., 2000), that
260 would have inhibited the lignocellulolytic microorganisms development (slow growth strategy),
261 such as *T. harzianum* (Naseby et al., 1999, 2000).

262 4.3. Quantification of *T. harzianum* T-78

263 In regards to the *T. harzianum* population, the low value observed at 30 DAS for all treatments
264 in the non-*F. oxysporum* infected growing media could be explained by natural competition with
265 autochthonous microorganisms present in the substrates. In the following two sampling times
266 (37 and 43 DAS), *T. harzianum* adapted to the new environment and overcame the initial
267 suppression. In the *F. oxysporum* infected growing media; this behaviour was not evident due
268 to the control mechanism against *F. oxysporum* by *T. harzianum*, which created competitive
269 growth of the fungal strains (Harman et al., 2004).

270 The difference of one order of magnitude of CFUs of *T. harzianum* within C1Th and C2Th water
271 extracts and their respective solid organic matrix (compost C1 and C2) can be attributed to the
272 lower amount of organic compounds in compost water extracts, which could have induced
273 sporulation of the fungal strain (Oliveira et al., 2008).

274 5. Conclusions

275 The data obtained demonstrated that the combination of citrus compost and the microorganism
276 of the genus *Trichoderma* sp. (*T. harzianum* T-78) can be used as a viable alternative as a partial
277 substitute for peat. Moreover, the advantages of the use of this substrate are not only limited
278 to the substitution of a non-renewable resource (peat) with products derived from organic
279 wastes, but also include the potential biocontrol effect against *Fusarium* wilt and the
280 exploitation of the nutritive effect of the compost – based growing media. However, to ensure
281 a valuable antagonistic effect under greenhouse nursery conditions, additional evaluations of
282 biocontrol agents and composts should be carried out under a wider range of conditions,
283 compost types and plant pathogens.

284 The development of the production and utilisation of compostbased growing media amended
285 with *T. harzianum* T-78 would reduce the exploitation of non-renewable peat and minimise the

286 application of chemicals (i.e. synthetic fertilisers and plant protection agents) during melon plant
287 production, thus enhancing its environmental sustainability.

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